

Influence of Temperature on the Carbon-Nitrogen Ratio of Soils.

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In a recent communication (Dhar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 883) it has been stated that just as carbohydrates preserve the body proteins from undergoing oxidation, the carbonaceous matter present in the soil is likely to protect the soil protein from oxidation. This retarding influence of carbonaceous compounds on the oxidation of proteins to ammonia, and ammonium salts to nitrites and nitrates, appears to be a general phenomenon occurring in chemical, catalytic, physiological, soil and photochemical oxidation processes in which a mixture of organic substances is undergoing oxidation in air. The retarding influence of carbonaceous compounds on the velocity of the oxidation of proteins seems to control the carbon-nitrogen ratio.

Moreover, the ratio of carbon to nitrogen to be oxidised from a system would also depend on the ease with which these compounds, existing in mixtures, can undergo oxidation. It has been also stated in the previous paper that in starvation, the ratio of carbon to nitrogen oxidised in the metabolism of different animals is also fairly constant and is not far from 10.

It is generally believed that in fever when the body temperature is higher than the normal, the protein metabolism is relatively greater than in normal health, as will be evident from the following lines, "From a study of the excretion of nitrogen, together with a comparison of carbon dioxide and oxygen in the expired air, it has been thought, that the increased oxidation in fever affects specially the nitrogenous or protein constituents of the body" (MacCallum, "A Text Book of Pathology", 1925, p. 157). It is expected, therefore, that the nitrogenous compounds present in the soil of a warm place is likely to be oxidised at a relatively greater speed than those present in the soil of a cool place and hence the carbon-nitrogen ratio of the compounds existing in the soil will be higher in a warm than in a cold country.

In order to prove the validity of this view point, we have determined the carbon-nitrogen ratio of different soils collected from Bengal Behar, United Provinces and the Punjab. The carbon and nitrogen were estimated according to the method of Robinson, McLean and Williams. (*J. Agric. Sci.*, 1929, 19, 315) by heating 5 g. of dry soil with strong sulphuric acid, anhydrous potassium sulphate and a few crystals of copper sulphate. The sulphur dioxide generated was absorbed in a standard solution of iodine. The nitrogen was determined by the liberation of ammonia on the addition of an excess of alkali to the solution obtained after oxidation by sulphuric acid. The following experimental results have been obtained.

TABLE I.

Bengal.

	Carbon.	Nitrogen.	Carbon/Nitrogen.
White rice fields (Nadia)	1.014%	0.112%	9.05
Red rice fields (Nadia)	0.849	0.096	8.84
Dacca soils			
Lab. No. 103 North Hazi Dacca Farm, unmanured under <i>Aman</i> paddy, surface soil	0.722	0.08	9.02
Lab. No. 104 Subhady, unmanured low <i>Aman</i> paddy land surface soil	1.372	0.146	9.39
Lab. No. 105 Bikrampur, uncropped, collected from the bank of a river, sub-soil	0.549	0.057	9.63
Lab. No. 106 Merida, unmanured <i>Boro</i> paddy very low land, surface soil	2.124	0.227	9.35
			Mean 9.14

TABLE II.
Behar (Pusa).

	Carbon.	Nitrogen.	Carbon/Nitrogen.
Permanent plot, complete manure collected in July 1932, analysed in April 1935	0.2913%	0.0313%	9.36
Do-Fresh soil collected in April 1935	0.3532	0.0406	8.7
Green manure, collected in July 1932, analysed in February, 1935	0.2331	0.025	9.32
Do-Fresh soil collected in April, 1935	0.2759	0.0332	8.31
No manure, collected in July 1932, analysed in February, 1935	0.2230	0.0238	9.37
Do-Fresh soil collected in April, 1935	0.2636	0.028	9.41
Green manure and super phosphate, collected in July 1932 analysed in April, 1935	0.248	0.0264	9.39
Do-Fresh soil collected and analysed in 1935	0.3509	0.0361	9.72
Farm yard manure collected in July 1932, analysed in April 1935	0.337	0.0313	10.8
Do-collected and analysed in April, 1935	0.3522	0.0361	9.75

Mean collected in July 1932=9.64.

Mean collected & analysed in April, 1935=9.17.

TABLE III.
United Provinces.

Allahabad.	Carbon.	(Uncultivated soils)	
		Nitrogen.	Carbon/Nitrogen.
1	0.4464%	0.0434%	10.2
2	0.4854	0.04375	11.09
3	0.4352	0.0388	11.21
4	0.5481	0.0467	11.7
5	0.589	0.05	11.76
6	0.3075	0.026	11.82
7	0.5055	0.0458	11.03
8	0.504	0.0424	11.88
9	0.5356	0.0486	11.02
		Mean	11.3

TABLE IV.

Punjab soil.

	Carbon.	Nitrogen.	Carbon/Nitrogen.
Chkanwali Reclamation, collected and analysed in 1935.	0.5774%	0.04%	14.43
Ranjit-Kot (Shekhpura) collected and analysed in 1935	0.6442	0.04375	14.2
Hiyatpur (Behwal) collec- ted and analysed in 1935	0.8464	0.0582	14.5
			Mean 14.37

The foregoing results show that the ratio of carbon to nitrogen is highest in the soil collected in the Punjab and the value is 14.37 and in the United Provinces it is 11.3. In Behar, it is 9.17 with freshly collected soils and 9.64 with soils collected in 1932 and analysed in 1935 and in Bengal, the ratio is 9.14,

The carbon-nitrogen ratio in soils of different countries seems to corroborate the above view point. The average ratio of 50 soils collected in England is 10. In Wales, the ratio is 9.2. In Washington state after long cultivation the ratio observed was 10.2. In Sudan the average is 12.6 and in Transval, it is 14.4 (compare Rusell "Soil Conditions and Plant Growth," 1932, p. 314). From the foregoing results, it can be concluded that the nitrogenous compounds present in the soil of a warm place is oxidised more readily than those present in the soil of a temperate climate, just as in fever, the protein metabolism is greater than in normal health.

In publications from these laboratories, it has been emphasised that the chemical reactions taking place in the oxidation of the substances present in soils need not be always caused by micro-organisms as has been hitherto believed but may be photochemical and catalytic. These views regarding the soil processes have recently been supported by Corbet (*Soil Sci.*, 1934, 38, 407), who has observed that the number of micro-organisms per grain of soil in the Malay Peninsula is only 500,000 as against 20 millions present in Rothamsted soils. He has made the following statements:—

"It has been submitted that, by permitting timber to decay on the site of clearing, a considerable amount of readily available soil, nitrogen is locked-up as a consequence of the addition to the soil of material with a very high carbon-nitrogen ratio. If such locking-up of nitrogen in the body material of micro-organisms occurred it would be reflected in an increased soil microbial population, but the results presented in this paper show that such population increases do not take place....."

It seems evident that the fall in the nitrogen content of the soil to a lower level on subjection to higher temperatures must be ascribed to chemical and not to microbiological agency." The carbon-nitrogen ratio in ordinary soils appears not to be regulated by the energy requirements of the micro-organisms but is controlled by the ease with which proteins, amino acids and ammonium salts are oxidised by air catalytically or photochemically in presence of carbonaceous compounds. The energy-rich substances like carbohydrates, cellulose, etc., added to the soil may not increase the number of micro-organisms and cause a locking-up of nitrogen as body material but always decrease the velocity of the oxidation of the soil nitrogenous compounds and thus the ammonia production in soil decreases in presence of carbohydrates, cellulose, etc.

SUMMARY.

1. Determinations of carbon-nitrogen ratio of soils collected in Bengal, Behar, United Provinces and the Punjab show that the value is highest in the Punjab and least in Bengal and Behar.

2. Results obtained in different countries show that this ratio in temperate climates is lower than that obtained in tropical climates.

3. Proteins present in the soil of a warm country are oxidised more readily than those present in a temperate climate, just as in fever the protein metabolism is relatively greater than in normal health. It appears that the oxidations taking place in the soil follow the same laws as those prevailing in animal metabolism, and the carbon-nitrogen ratio in soils is not an outcome of the microbial activity as has been hitherto believed.

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